

VACCINATED? TESTING STILL MATTERS!

Even with the growing rate of COVID-19 vaccinations in the US, testing is still an essential tool to help control the pandemic and ultimately end it.

5 REASONS TO TEST:

2. Prevent a resurgence

Many experts believe it's unlikely that COVID-19 will ever disappear completely. Even if it circulates at very low levels, we need to understand where it is, how it might be changing, and how these changes might lead to future public health problems.

3. Track variants

The virus that causes COVID-19 will continue to mutate, and new genetic variants will emerge. Continued testing can help catch worrisome variants early.

4. Adjust safety precautions

Testing can help public health officials gauge whether vaccinations are working to protect people from the worst effects of the disease and controlling the emergence of variants, and whether variants are getting more contagious or having more severe impact. If cases begin to rise, schools, offices, and other places where people gather may need to change their mask policies, enforce greater social distancing, or improve ventilation.

5. Assist where vaccination rates are lower

Testing remains an important tool especially in communities and areas where vaccination rates are not yet high enough to effectively reduce virus spread.

1. Treat high-risk cases early

Vaccinated people can still get COVID-19, though usually those infections won't require hospitalization or lead to death. However, for people at a high risk for getting very sick from COVID-19, catching infection early is key, so healthcare providers can consider treatment that can be effective when started in the very early days of an infection.

